

1 **An expression screen to identify genes important for trastuzumab resistance: Abca5.**

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6 We measured total transcription by RNA-sequencing in patients sensitive or resistant to treatment with
7 trastuzumab for HER2+ breast cancer for discovery of genes that confer or support resistance to
8 HER2-targeted therapies in humans. In this manuscript we describe identification of Abca5 as a candidate
9 gene product of the trastuzumab resistance gene expression signature.

10 Citations

11 1. Kubo, Y., Sekiya, S., Ohigashi, M., Takenaka, C., Tamura, K., Nada, S., Nishi, T., Yamamoto, A.
12 and Yamaguchi, A., 2005. ABCA5 resides in lysosomes, and ABCA5 knockout mice develop lysosomal
13 disease-like symptoms. *Molecular and cellular biology*, 25(10), pp.4138-4149.